

Beyond Explanation: Deadlock Situations as a Stress Test for Human-Centered XAI in Automated Vehicles

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Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI) assumes that improving explanation quality enhances user understanding and supports appropriate trust calibration. While this assumption holds in stable contexts, it becomes insufficient in safety-critical domains such as automated mobility. In SAE Level 4 automated driving, users supervise autonomous systems rather than actively control them. In ambiguous traffic situations, vehicles may hesitate or repeatedly reassess the environment, creating “deadlock” scenarios. In such moments, users evaluate not only why the system acted, but whether it appears confident, stable, and capable of resolving uncertainty. This position paper argues that deadlock situations expose a missing dimension in HCXAI: the need for visible initiative and temporally structured coordination. I propose deadlock as a stress test for HCXAI and outline how temporal initiative signaling may influence trust calibration more strongly than explanation fidelity alone.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **HCI theory, concepts and models**; **Interactive systems and tools**; **Interaction design process and methods**; **Collaborative and social computing**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Human-Centered Explainable AI, Trust Calibration, Temporal Coordination, Deadlock Scenarios, Automated Driving, Safety-Critical Interaction

1 Introduction

Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI) seeks to make AI systems transparent, understandable, and trustworthy. A central assumption is that clearer explanations improve user understanding and support appropriate trust. While this holds in stable settings, it becomes less sufficient in safety-critical domains such as automated mobility, where system behavior unfolds in real time and under uncertainty. In SAE Level 4 automation [5], vehicles perform the complete driving task within defined operational domains. Human occupants are no longer active drivers but supervisors of autonomous systems. Although the vehicle is responsible for control, passengers continue to monitor its behavior. They interpret hesitation, unexpected maneuvers, and pauses as signals. Trust therefore depends not only on what the system explains, but also on how it signals control, confidence, and initiative [6].

Across my prior work on in-vehicle intelligent agents [3], data transparency in vehicular digital twins [1], and interpretable risk detection models [2], a consistent pattern emerged: transparency improves awareness, but does not fully resolve coordination challenges in dynamic situations. Breakdown situations make this limitation visible. In ambiguous traffic scenarios, automated vehicles may hesitate or repeatedly reassess the environment. Users then ask less “Why did the system decide this?” and more “Is the system in control?” and “What happens next?”. I argue that such deadlock situations act as stress tests for HCXAI. They reveal a missing dimension in explanation-centered approaches: visible initiative and temporally structured coordination under uncertainty.

2 Explanation vs. Coordination

Much of HCXAI research assumes that if users understand why a system made a decision, they can interact with it appropriately. Explanations clarify system reasoning and support trust calibration. However, explanation primarily addresses cognitive alignment. It does not necessarily support coordination in dynamic and uncertain environments. In

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Manuscript submitted to ACM

Level 4 automated vehicles, passengers interpret hesitation and sudden changes as indicators of system competence [7]. Coordination concerns initiative, timing, and mutual awareness: Who acts next? Is the system confident? Is the situation under control? These questions are relational and temporal rather than purely cognitive.

Empirical findings support this distinction. Critical vehicle-status information can increase trust [3], and transparency mechanisms are strongly preferred [1]. Yet users remain uncertain about how the system will behave in complex situations. Similarly, interpretable machine learning models can detect risk-relevant patterns [2], but technical interpretability does not guarantee perceived stability in real-time interaction. These observations challenge a core assumption in HCXAI: that explanation fidelity alone predicts trust calibration. Deadlock situations suggest that temporal initiative signaling may be a stronger predictor of perceived control and system competence than explanation quality alone. Current HCXAI evaluation frameworks rarely account for such temporal coordination under uncertainty.

XAI research already considers actionability and supports users in deciding how to respond after receiving an explanation. However, in Level 4 automated driving, users often cannot intervene or resolve the situation themselves (specially in case of robotaxis). In deadlock scenarios, the primary user question is therefore not “What should I do after seeing the explanation?”, but “What will the system do next and is it in control?”. This shifts the role of explainability from supporting user decision-making to supporting coordination under uncertainty.

3 Deadlock as a Stress Test

Deadlock situations expose the limits of explanation-centered design. Consider a Level 4 vehicle approaching a temporary construction zone. It slows down, moves slightly forward, pauses again, and repeatedly reassesses the environment. Technically, the system remains within its operational limits. From the user’s perspective, however, the behavior may appear uncertain. An explanation such as “Obstacle detected” clarifies perception but does not indicate what will happen next. Users evaluate whether hesitation reflects caution or confusion, and whether escalation is imminent. The issue is not a lack of explanation, but a lack of visible initiative and temporal guidance. This perspective raises key design questions: How should AI systems communicate uncertainty without signaling loss of control? How can systems make intended next actions legible? When should escalation be framed as cooperative strategy rather than failure?

My upcoming study investigates these questions using scripted deadlock scenarios in Level 4 automated driving. The study compares explanatory signaling with initiative-oriented signaling to examine how each shapes perceived control and trust calibration.

4 Conclusion

This position paper argues that explanation alone is not sufficient in safety-critical systems. Deadlock situations in automated mobility reveal this limitation. Users evaluate not only why a system acts, but whether it appears stable, predictable, and capable of resolving ambiguity. This aligns with broader discussions in human-AI interaction that call for moving beyond static explainability toward dynamic and cooperative system behavior [4]. This perspective invites discussion within the HCXAI community:

- Should escalation be considered part of explainability, or a distinct interaction layer?
- How can AI systems communicate uncertainty without undermining perceived competence?
- What interaction patterns signal confidence versus hesitation?
- How can initiative be designed to support trust calibration in the absence of user control?

These questions directly inform my upcoming study and contribute to broader HCXAI discussions on how XAI behaves under real-time uncertainty. Deadlock does not invalidate explainability. Rather, it clarifies that explanation must be integrated into a broader ecosystem of coordination, initiative, and temporally structured interaction design.

5 Acknowledgments

This publication has been supported by the Excellence in Digital Sciences and Interdisciplinary Technologies (EXDIGIT) project, funded by Land Salzburg under the grant number 20204-WISS/263/6-6022.

The author used OpenAI's ChatGPT to support language improvements and structural revisions during the writing process. All content was reviewed and verified by the author.

References

- [1] Cansu Demir, Nicola Leschke, Glenda Hannibal, Mahdi Akil, and Alexander Meschtscherjakov. 2025. Understanding Driver Expectations and Preferences Around Data Transparency in Vehicular Digital Twins. In *Adjunct Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Automotive User Interfaces and Interactive Vehicular Applications (AutomotiveUI Adjunct '25)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 227–232. doi:10.1145/3744335.3758509
- [2] Cansu Demir, Narges Mehran, and Alexander Meschtscherjakov. 2025. Student Research Track: Twin the Drive: An HGBR-based Machine Learning Model as a Vehicular Digital Twin for Risk Detection. In *Adjunct Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Automotive User Interfaces and Interactive Vehicular Applications (AutomotiveUI Adjunct '25)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 373–376. doi:10.1145/3744335.3762326
- [3] Cansu Demir, Alexander Meschtscherjakov, and Magdalena Gärtner. 2024. Unlocking Trust and Acceptance in Tomorrow's Ride: How In-Vehicle Intelligent Agents Redefine SAE Level 5 Autonomy. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction* 8, 12 (2024). doi:10.3390/mti8120111
- [4] Upol Ehsan, Q. Vera Liao, Samir Passi, Mark O. Riedl, and III Daumé, Hal. 2024. Seamless XAI: Operationalizing Seamless Design in Explainable AI. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 8, CSCW1, Article 119 (April 2024), 29 pages. doi:10.1145/3637396
- [5] SAE International. 9/23. Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems for On-Road Motor Vehicles. https://www.sae.org/standards/content/j3016_202104/.
- [6] Diah Ayu Irawati, Elif Bölükbaşı, Michael A. Gerber, and Andreas Riener. 2024. The role of Explainable AI in the Design of Visual Texts for Trust Calibration in Level 3 Automated Vehicles. In *Adjunct Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Automotive User Interfaces and Interactive Vehicular Applications (Stanford, CA, USA) (AutomotiveUI '24 Adjunct)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 300–303. doi:10.1145/3641308.3680514
- [7] Marcel Walch, Kristin Mühl, Johannes Kraus, Tanja Stoll, Martin Baumann, and Michael Weber. 2017. *From Car-Driver-Handovers to Cooperative Interfaces: Visions for Driver-Vehicle Interaction in Automated Driving*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 273–294. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-49448-7_10